
A REVIEW OF KINETIC MODEL EVALUATION FOR ANAEROBIC DIGESTION PROCESS

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ABSTRACT: *Variability of process conditions, diversity of bio-sourced feedstock as well as the slow and unstable nature of the process make anaerobic digestion (AD) technology, a subject of recent research despite several centuries of its practice. Model is one of the tools exploited not only to predict the system's performance but also for improved production. The search for appropriate models is currently a major priority for optimizing the process and the literature is flooded on this subject. This paper reviewed the prominent ones among them from mathematical, experimental and statistical background. It was found that despite the practicality of the exponential model when complemented by the Monod's model, in describing AD process, the mathematical models failed to describe cell behavior at stationary phase. Knowledge of cell behavior in this phase is significantly relevant especially when high retention times and 'digestate' valorization are desired. Hence, the emergence of Gompertz (statistical) models which tends to describe cell growth rate during stationary phase. However, the complexity of the Gompertz models and the inadequacy of mathematical model beyond growth phase led to development of experimental models which do not focus on the growth rate but on the kinetics of substrate degradation or product formation. Specifically, first-order kinetic models, model based on transfer function, and cone model emanating from different types of substrates and combinations in co-digestion have been formulated. Evaluation of these models is critical and requires both the coefficient of determination of the fit (r^2) and the root mean squares errors (RMSE). Based on gas potential generated, it is found that anaerobic digestion processes are more of waste management/treatment strategy than energy production irrespective of the substrate combo as energy generation is relatively less than that of the conventional energy.*

Keywords: *Anaerobic Digestion Models, Exponential, Monod, Gompertz Biokinetic Model*

1.0: Introduction

Digestion is a biology term relating to eating of food and biodigestion connotes a special type of eating by microbes. In view of this, digestion is a biological process in which a consortium of micro-organisms convert biological material (organic matter) into volatile components (biogas) and water resulting to mass loss and perhaps destruction of pathogens. Biodigestion technology was originally formulated for waste treatment/disposal to address one of the global issues posed by its counterparts: pyrolysis, gasification and thermal incineration (combustion) with respect to greenhouse effect (Arvanitoyannis *et al.*, 2007; Cheng *et al.*, 2010). Hence, it is also known as sludge digestion. However, due to exponential demand in energy and corresponding increase in waste generation, biodigestion technology is not only for waste disposal/treatment but a linkage to implementation of Waste to Energy (WtE) strategy.

Furthermore, the technology offers one of the best and most soil-friendly fertilizers while making the environment pollution cum pathogen free (Johari *et al.*, 2012). Generally, sludge digestion may involve decomposition of biological material by microbes in the presence of oxygen (aerobic digestion) or in the absence of oxygen (anaerobic digestion). In aerobic digestion, microbes utilize bio-sourced feedstocks in the presence of oxygen and the end products are mainly CO₂ and water which are stable oxidized forms of carbon and hydrogen. If the organic material contains Nitrogen and Sulphur, the end product may also include Ammonia/Nitrate and Sulphate. The process is cheap and it is useful in disposing waste as mass of the digestible waste reduces. However, the effluent is stable but not much useful to crops as fertilizers since Nitrogen in the digestate is converted to ammonia gas which is not accessible to plant (Bhat *et al.*, 2001). Moreover, the process is not efficient for energy generation. On the other hand, Anaerobic Biodigestion (AD) Technology involves digestion of biomaterials by microbes (anaerobes) in an oxygen-deficient chamber (digester). The process produces methane, a major combustible constituent in biogas, in addition to CO₂. However, there are two types of anaerobic digestions depending on the solid content of the slurry to process. These are: wet digestion and dry digestion. Anaerobic digestion is considered dry if the total solid content is above 50% of the slurry while the wet digestion involves more than 50% of water in the slurry (Teng 2014). Wet digestion is more efficient than the dry counterpart as it gives high quality products (Zhang, 2017).

Although, aerobic digestion is cheaper and easy to maintain than AD, studies revealed that the latter has an edge over the former as the biogas and the super biofertilizer generated during anaerobic degradation adequately compensate, economically to the challenges confronting the process (Bhat *et al.*, 2001; Vavilinet *et al.*, 2008). In addition, Suh and Roussaux (2002) stated that AD has the least aggressive effect on the environment compared to its counterparts (aerobic, pyrolysis, incineration, combustion, etc.) and as well proffer solution to the energy crisis and climate change leaving the environment pollution-free when properly handled (Bah *et al.*, 2014). Obviously, anaerobic digestion is one of the most advantageous waste disposal/treatment methods. This method of waste disposal not only provide biofuel for local energy needs but also bio-fertilizer to support crop growth (Chynoweth *et al.*, 1998).

AD is an age-long process known for centuries. However, it is still a subject of research interest due to variability of process conditions in which it can be operated, diversity of raw materials and influential factors (Agyeman and Tao 2014; Fu *et al.*, 2015; Di Maria *et al.*, 2015; Belle *et al.*, 2015; Aboudiet *et al.*, 2015; Glanprach and Annachatre, 2016; Dennehy *et al.*, 2016; Aboudiet *et al.*, 2016; Li *et al.*, 2017; Zahan *et al.*, 2017; Mancini *et al.*, 2018;

Franco *et al.*, 2018; Guo *et al.*, 2018; Martín *et al.*, 2018; Mustafa *et al.*, 2018; Vazifekhoran *et al.*, 2018; Xu *et al.*, 2018). The progress achieved so far is attributed to increasing interest in new bio-sourced (raw) materials spanning through the first generation to the most recent fourth generation bio-sourced feedstock (Edenseting *et al.*, 2020).

As one of the most energy-efficient and environmentally beneficial technologies recognized worldwide, a thorough understanding of the phenomena involved in AD process is necessary. The process is attractive but it is considered slow and unstable process couple with low extent of degradation due to the strict nature of the anaerobes (Batstone *et al.*, 2007; Ofoefule and Uzodinma, 2006; Ofoefule and Uzodinma, 2009; Ofoefule and Onukwuli, 2010; Rajendran *et al.*, 2013). In view of these challenges, there is a growing research interest aimed at improving the process and the literature is flooded on the subject (Weiland, 2010; Nzila *et al.*, 2012; Gwavuya *et al.*, 2012; Rajendran *et al.*, 2013; Buysman and Mol, 2013; Kabir *et al.*, 2013; Landi *et al.*, 2013; Tigabu *et al.*, 2013; Laramée *et al.*, 2013; Fedailaine *et al.*, 2015; Velazquez-Martí *et al.*, 2019). Model development is one of the tools exploited to acquire deep understanding of the process. It is carried out using basic principles of Chemical Engineering in order to establish characteristic parameters of the bio-material and process conditions to predict the system's evolution over time, the performance obtained, and fermentation speed (Velazquez-Martí *et al.*, 2019). The essence of these models is beyond understanding the process better but they exploited for process optimization for improved production. The search for appropriate models is now a major priority for optimizing the AD process. Currently, several models associated with AD process are often very complex and not suitable for optimization (Simeonov and Stoyanov, 2003; Fedailaine *et al.*, 2015). This paper reviews some of these valuable models. It is expected that the models would be harnessed for optimization of the process and as well proffer solutions problems challenging the technology.

2.0 Advance in Anaerobic Digestion Technology: A Prelude to its Modelling

Modeling anaerobic digestion process is an herculean task as it involves an in-depth study of the process, monitoring the time evolution of the composition of the biogas produced during the transformation of the organic matter. The process has been investigated for years and tremendous impacts have been achieved. The myriad of research on AD process conducted is attributed to the diversity of bio-sourced feedstock available and several influential factors such as: the process condition, inoculum and pre-treatment of feedstock (Kozo *et al.*, 1996; Zuru *et al.*, 1998; Bamgboye, 2012). Table 1 summarized some of advances achieved so far.

Table 1: Advances in Anaerobic Digestion Process

Source: Velazquez-Marti *et al.* (2019)

Researcher	Bio-Sourced Feedstock	Process Condition	Gas Potential (m ³ /kgSV)
Bayrakdar <i>et al.</i> 2018	Chicken manure	Mesophilic	0.272
Franco <i>et al.</i> 2018	Wheat straw + inoculum	Mesophilic	0.229
Franco <i>et al.</i> 2018	Wheat straw + glucose + ac. Formic + Inoculums	Mesophilic	0.276
Guo <i>et al.</i> 2018	Excessively withered corn straw + glucose	Mesophilic	0.282
Li <i>et al.</i> 2018	Parton + sheep manure	Mesophilic	0.152
Li <i>et al.</i> 2018	Paper + sheep manure	Mesophilic	0.199
Mancini <i>et al.</i> 2018	Lignocellulose in general	N-methylmorpholine N-oxide	0.304
Martín <i>et al.</i> 2018	Microalgae + pig manure	Alkaline pretreatment with NAOH	0.377
Mustafa <i>et al.</i> 2018	Bagasse of sugarcane + inoculum*	Hydrothermal pretreatment	0.318
Vazifehkhora <i>et al.</i> 2018	Wheat straw + sewage	Mesophilic	0.314
Xu <i>et al.</i> 2018	Corn straw + Bacillus Subtilis	Microaerobic mesolithic	0.270
Zahan <i>et al.</i> 2018	Gallinaza (sawdust, wood shavings, and rice or straw husk) with yogurt serum	Mesophilic	0.670
Aboudi <i>et al.</i> 2016	Dry sediment of sugar beet tails + pig Manure	Mesophilic	0.260
Dennehy <i>et al.</i> 2016	Food waste and pig manure	Mesophilic	0.521
Glanpracha and Annachhatre, 2016	Cassava pulp with pig manure	Mesophilic	0.380
Marin <i>et al.</i> 2015	Vinasse and chicken manure (chicken dung)	Mesophilic	0.650
Aboudi <i>et al.</i> 2015	Dry beet granules of sugar beet + cow dung	Mesophilic	0.280
Belle <i>et al.</i> 2015	Fodder radish with cow dung	Mesophilic	0.200
Cestonaro <i>et al.</i> 2015	Sheep litter (mixture of rice husk with feces and urine) + cattle manure	Mesophilic	0.171
Di Maria <i>et al.</i> 2015	Sludge from wastewater with fruit and vegetable waste	Mesophilic	0.216
Fu <i>et al.</i> 2015a	Corn straw + inoculum	Thermophilic microaerobic	0.326
Fu <i>et al.</i> 2015b	Corn straw + inoculum	Secondary thermophilic microaerobic	0.381
Agyeman and Tao, 2014	Food waste + livestock manure	Mesophilic	0.467

Currently, AD processes are carried out using mixture of different classes of bio-sourced feedstock that ferment better together than separately due to their enriched microbial load. In this way, their nutritional needs are better complemented. This process is called co-digestion and improved biogas generation has been reported from the substrate combo (Uzodinma *et al.*, 2007; Batstone *et al.*, 2007; Ofoefule and Uzodinma, 2009; Oparaku *et al.*, 2013). Furthermore, studies have been carried out on novel inocula and their interaction with bio-sourced feedstock as well as their nutritional requirements (Cestonaro *et al.*, 2015; Fu *et al.*, 2015). Research on pretreatment of bio-sourced feedstock are equally being conducted (Tchobanoglous *et al.*, 2003; Fekadu, 2014). Studies on thermal effect on the AD process, alternating thermophilic, mesophilic and psychrophilic stages while evaluating the productivity, kinetics, and net energy balance have been adequately investigated (Ampomah-Benefo, 2018; Velazquez-Marti *et al.*, 2019).

However, based on biomethane potential, AD process is classified into 3 groups (Velazquez-Marti *et al.*, 2019). These are: low-production, medium-production and high-production processes. The values of biomethane potential (Table 1) reported from various anaerobic digestion studies carried out in mesophilic conditions (between 30 and 37°C) show that methane production in most cases ranges between 0.15 and 0.65 m³ kg⁻¹SV. Based on this classification, the quantity of biomethane produced in each of the processes is tabulated as seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Classification of Anaerobic Digestion Process Based on Biomethane Potential

S/N	Classes of AD Process	Biomethane Potential (m ³ kg ⁻¹ SV)
1	Low-Production Processes	0.15 - 0.30
2	Medium-Production Processes	0.30 - 0.45
3	High-Production Processes	< 0.45

It is obvious that these types of energy productions and their energy equivalence when compared to the conventional energy source indicated that anaerobic digestion processes are more of waste disposal or treatment process with a complementary energy product than as an alternative energy source to the problems derived from the limitation of fossil fuels (Velazquez-Marti *et al.*, 2019).

3.0: Fundamental Principle of Anaerobic Digestion Models (ADM)

The progress recorded so far in AD process is a brainchild of several researchers from various background. Specifically, microbiology, biochemistry and Engineering contributed immensely in advancing the technology. The nitty-gritty of anaerobic biogas production technology in terms of its biochemical and physicochemical mechanisms are broken down into four stages (Figure 1): hydrolysis, acidogenesis (acidification), acetogenesis and methanogenesis (Krich, 2005; Zhang, 2017).

Figure 1: Metabolic pathways and microbial groups in anaerobic digestion
Source: Mara and Horan (2003)

This process requires little energy while the rest of the energy is stored as biogas and nutrient-rich sludge (Wagner *et al.*, 2009; Herrmann *et al.*, 2016; Capson-Tojo *et al.*, 2017). The stages as represented in Figure 2 are interconnected as the product formed in each of the stages becomes the substrate of the subsequent stage. The hydrolytic phase initiates the biodegradation/biodigestion process and it mainly a catabolic process in which polymers of long carbon chains are broken obtaining shorter acid chains. This stage is usually the rate limiting stage for lignocellulosic materials (Saha and Cotta, 2007; Vavilin *et al.*, 2008). Subsequently, an acetogenic phase, in which the short-chain acids obtained in the previous phase are transformed into acetic acid. It is considered to be the stage with fastest reaction rate (Saha and Cotta, 2007). This is attributed to the fact that many organisms are more active during this stage than during the other stages.

Figure 2: Stages in anaerobic digestion

Many researchers considered acidification-acetogenesis to be a single stage making 3 stages in all (Capson-Tojo *et al.*, 2017). However, this paper recognized these stages (separately) as different products (acids and acetates) are formed. Finally, a methanogenic phase, in which the acetic acid is transformed into methane. It is perhaps the rate limiting stage, strictly anaerobic and methane forming stage (Conrad, 1999; Ferry, 2011; Ampomah-Benefo, 2018). However, each of these stages is provided by a differentiated microbiological groups. These are: acidogens, acetogens and methanogens. Each group takes as a substrate to the product generated in the previous phase hydrolysis, acidogenesis (acidification), acetogenesis and methanogenesis. The most sensitive and strict bacteria (anaerobes) responsible for methane formation are methanogens.

A critical analysis of the evolution these microbial groups in a batch-type reactor, in batches, the variation of cell concentration varies (Figure 3). Initially, the concentration of microorganisms responsible of digestion is small and evolves very slowly in this stage because it needs time to adapt.

Figure 3: Growth phases of typical microbes in an anaerobic system

The initial phase (\overline{AD}) occurs when the cells are inactive. It is called lag phase (lethargy). This is followed by a rapid increase in cell concentration called exponential growth phase (\overline{DB}). However, the growth phase reaches its climax when substrate concentration is depleted (almost exhausted) such that the microbes compete for substrate. Consequently, the number of cell replications equates its death rate, so the number of living cells is stabilized. This phase is called the stationary phase (\overline{BC}). The stationary phase ends when this battle for substrate causes a higher number of deaths than the number of reproductions, resulting in cell concentration to fall sharply. This phase is called the cell death phase.

Obviously, the lag phase is expected as the hydrolysis stage is exploited to solubilize the substrate. It is carried out through extracellular enzymes excreted by certain bacteria. This is a biochemical process not purely a biological process as there is no metabolism (Guo *et al.*, 2018). The catabolism process is catalyzed by the enzymes (a biochemical substance excreted by microbes). However, the acidogenic, acetogenesis and methanogenesis are metabolic steps where the organic substrate is consumed and converted by bacteria. This translates to the emergence of microbial activity beyond lag phase. From the foregoing, it is generally

accepted that AD is a multi-stage microbiological process. This is the principle in which AD models are developed.

4.0: ADM: Development and Classification

The remarkable feat achieved so far in advancing AD process is attributed to consistent research effort in understanding the process deeply. Consequently, several models have been developed depicting the process. The pioneer of them is the mathematical model. It developed based on the fundamental principle behind the process as presented in section 3. The development of the mathematical model is presented in section 4.1. This is followed by classification of ADM (section 4.2).

4.1 Development of Anaerobic Digestion Models

Model can be defined as mathematical expression that describes the behavior of a system. It is developed to capture the essential aspects of an existing system. The complex physical interaction in the system as well as the causes and effects between system variables are clearly understood by modeling. Models can be theoretical (white box) as in mathematical models or empirical (black box) as in experimental models. Modelling the AD process is one of the strategies exploited to gain a better insight of the overall process which eventually translates to improve process design (Shack *et al.*, 1989; Obonukutet *et al.*, 2015; Ojo *et al.*, 2018).

A model widely used to describe the variation of cell concentration in the growth phase (Figure 3) has been the exponential model. This model is based on the hypothesis that the speed of growth in an instant is proportional to the concentration of cells existing at that moment. This is expressed mathematically by Equation (1), where X is the concentration of cells and μ is the constant of proportionality called cell growth rate:

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = \mu \cdot X \quad (1)$$

The development of Equation (1) when integrated shows that, in the growth phase, the variation of cells follows an exponential curve:

$$\frac{dX}{X} = \mu \cdot dt \quad \Rightarrow \int_{X_1}^{X_2} \frac{dX}{X} = \int_{t_{lag}}^t \mu \cdot dt \quad \Rightarrow \ln \frac{X_2}{X_1} = \mu \cdot (t - t_{lag})$$

Where: t_{lag} is the lag time. The cell growth rate has as unit the inverse of time (d^{-1}) and can be determined experimentally using Equation (2):

$$\mu = \frac{X_2 - X_1}{X_1} \quad (2)$$

However, the model is not completely satisfactory as μ has been found to be not constant as it varies with time as digestion progresses (Velazquez-Marti *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, as competition for the substrate increases, the curve in Figure 3 moves away from the exponential. Hence, the exponential model failed to describe the process beyond the growth phase.

Monod's Model emerged to address the deviation from the exponential curve. To achieve a better fit, Monod proposed a model for evaluating the cell growth rate as a function of the substrate concentration according to Equation (3), where S is the substrate

concentration at a given time, μ_{max} is the maximum rate of cell growth, and K_s is a constant called saturation:

$$\mu = \frac{\mu_{max} \cdot S}{K_s + S} \quad (3)$$

In addition, the Monod model proposes the existence of a maximum cell growth rate and a saturation constant that are characteristics of microbial species growing under defined conditions. The maximum growth rate is the one that occurs initially in the growth phase exponentially. When the substrate begins to be scarce, the rate decreases with respect to the maximum. Hence, deviation from exponential model sets in. The relationship between the variations of cell concentration is always proportional to substrate consumption (Velazquez-Martí *et al.*, 2019). The proportionality constant is called the biomass/substrate yield $Y_{x/s}$ and is defined by Equation (4), where S_0 and S_1 are the initial and final substrate concentrations and X_0 and X_1 are the initial and final cell concentrations:

$$Y_{x/s} = \frac{X_1 - X_0}{S_0 - S_1} \quad (4)$$

However, if the initial concentration of substrate (S_0) is known, the variation of cell mass during the process can be evaluated from the biomass/substrate ratio of the process $Y_{x/s}$. Limiting the decrease in the growth rate to a certain percentage of its maximum value allows calculating the time retention (RT) in a bioreactor batch as shown in Equation 5.

$$\begin{aligned} Z \cdot \mu_{max} &= \frac{\mu_{max} S_1}{K_s + S_1} \quad (0 < z < 1) \rightarrow S_1 = \frac{z}{1-z} \cdot K_s \\ Y_{x/s} &= \frac{X_1 - X_0}{S_0 - S_1} \rightarrow X_1 = X_0 + Y_{x/s} \cdot (S_0 - S_1) \\ &\quad \ln \frac{X_1}{X_0} \mu_{max} \cdot (RT - t_{lag}) \\ RT &= t_{lag} + \frac{1}{\mu_{max}} \ln \frac{X_1}{X_0} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The amount of product generated per unit volume and time (P) and methane in this case (M) are proportional to the variation of cell concentration (X). The proportionality constant $Y_{p/x}$ is called product/biomass yield (Equation 6):

$$Y_{p/x} = \frac{P_1 - P_0}{X_1 - X_0} \quad (6)$$

Where: X_0 represents the initial cell concentration in the reactor; X represents cell concentration at a time t, and t_{lag} is the time of lethargy or cellular adaptation. There are several model developed that supported Monod model. These are presented in next.

4.2: Classification of Anaerobic Digestion Models

Several models have been developed in an attempt to describe anaerobic digestion satisfactorily. The inability of the exponential model to vividly describe the process led to the formulation of Monod model. There are other monodlike models in the literature. Some of them are mostly empirical (experimental) models. This section presents the popular ones among them based on the class they belong (Table 3).

Table 3: Classes of Anaerobic Digestion Models

Mathematical Models		
S/N	Author/Name	Model
1	Exponential	$\mu = \frac{X_2 - X_1}{X_1(t - t_{lag})}$
2	Monod	$\mu = \frac{\mu_{max} S}{K_S + S}$
Kinetic Models without Inhibition		
S/N	Author/Name	Model
1	Tessier	$\mu = \mu_{max}(1 - e^{-S/K_S})$
2	Moser	$\mu = \mu_{max} \frac{S^n}{K_S a + S^n}$
3	Contois	$\mu = \mu_{max} \frac{S}{B X + S}$
Kinetic Models with Inhibition		
S/N	Author/Name	Model
1	Andrews and Noak	$\mu = \mu_{max} \frac{1}{K_S + S + \frac{S^2}{K_{is}}}$
2	Webb	$\mu = \mu_{max} \frac{S \cdot (1 + \frac{\beta \cdot S}{K_{is}})}{K_S + S + \frac{S^2}{K_{is}}}$
3	Aiba	$\mu = \mu_{max} \frac{S}{K_S + S} e^{-S/K_{is}}$
4	Teissier	$\mu = \mu_{max} [e^{-S/K_{is}} - e^{-S/K_S}]$
5	Tseng and Wymann	$\mu = \mu_{max} \frac{S}{K_S + S} - K_{Si}(S - S_C)$
Gompertz Model		
S/N	Author/Name	Model
1	Winsor	$\mu = C \ln a/X$
2	Zwietering	$\mu_{max} = c(a/e)$

4.2.1: Mathematical (Theoretical) Models

These models were developed based on first principles and provided the framework in which other models are built on. The models in this categories are:

Exponential model: The model describes the changes in cell concentration to be exponential [$X_2 = X_1 e^{\mu(t-t_{lag})}$]. It equally considered μ being constant. However, the above are not valid. As competition for substrate increases, the exponential growth ceases. Moreover, μ is equally not constant as it varies with time. The model's parameters include: t and t_{lag} for time and latency (lag) time respectively. μ for the cell growth rate. X_1, X_2 for cells' concentration prior and after digestion respectively.

Monod model: The model describes the existence of maximum cell growth rate indicating that the exponential growth is not indefinite. However, does not describe well the variation of cell concentration as the substrate is being consumed and the stationary phase approaches.

The model's parameters include: μ for the cell growth rate, S for substrate concentration, K_S is a constant for saturation and μ_{max} for maximum rate of cell growth.

Nevertheless, despite the practicality of the exponential model when complemented by the Monod equation and widely accepted by scholars in describing AD process, it is not completely satisfactory because it does not describe well the variation of cell concentration as the substrate is being consumed as the stationary phase approaches. Cell growth rate in this area (stationary phase) is significantly relevant high retention times (RT) is desired.

4.2 Gompertz (Statistical) Models

Interest in understanding cell growth rate beyond the exponential phase led to the development of Gompertz model. To find an adequate adjustment function for all phases of the process, Winsor (1932) proposes to use an equation developed by Gompertz (2011) in human demography. This proposes a model that considers the variable cell growth rate, as shown in Equations (7) and (8), where a and c are constants:

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = c \cdot \ln(a/X) \cdot X \quad (7)$$

$$\mu = c \cdot \ln(a/X) \quad (8)$$

According to Eq. (6), Gompertz moves radically away from the Monod approach, since the cell growth rate has no maximum. If there was a maximum, the derivative of Equation (8) would be canceled at some point, something that does not happen:

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow 0} \mu = \lim_{X \rightarrow 0} c \cdot \ln(a/X) = \infty$$

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \mu = \lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} c \cdot \ln(a/X) = -\infty$$

$$\frac{d\mu}{dt} = c \frac{X}{a} \cdot \left(\frac{-a}{X^2} \right) = \frac{-c}{X}$$

To obtain the function of cell concentration in time according to Gompertz, solving the differential equation [Equation (7)], using separable variables:

$$\frac{X}{X \cdot \ln(a/X)} = c \cdot dt$$

$$\int_{x_0}^x \frac{dX}{X \cdot \ln(a/X)} = \int_0^t c \cdot dt$$

$$- \left[\ln \left(\ln \frac{a}{X} \right) - \ln \left(\ln \frac{a}{X_0} \right) \right] = ct$$

$$\ln \left(\frac{\ln \frac{a}{X_0}}{\ln \frac{a}{X}} \right) = ct$$

$$\frac{\ln \frac{a}{X_0}}{e^{ct}} = \ln \frac{a}{X}$$

Since a and X_0 are constants, hence, the following consideration can be exploited:

$$\ln \frac{a}{X_0} = B = e^b$$

$$e^{e^{-a+b}} = \frac{a}{X_0}$$

Thus, the cellular concentration (X) in the reactor for each instant can be described by Equation (9).

$$X = a \cdot e^{[-e^{-ct+b}]} \quad (9)$$

Analyzing the limits in zero and infinity, it can be seen that the initial concentration of cells is X_1 and that the constant (a) represents an asymptote corresponding to the maximum cell potential, which would occur in the steady state:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} X = a \cdot e^{-B} = a \cdot e^{\ln \frac{X_0}{a}} = X_0$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} X = a$$

Modified Gompertz model

There were some modifications to Gompertz model. Prominent among them are:

Zwietering *et al.* (1990) suggest modifications providing physical meaning to Gompertz model's variables. The rate of growth can be redefined as stated in Equation (10):

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = a \cdot e^{[-e^{-ct+b}]} \cdot (-e^{-ct+b}) \cdot -c = a \cdot c \cdot e^{[-e^{-ct+b}]} \cdot e^{-ct+b}$$

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = a \cdot c \cdot e^{[-e^{-ct+b}]} \cdot e^{-ct+b} \quad (10)$$

The instant in which the maximum growth velocity t_m occurs would be evaluated from the first derivative of the velocity equal to zero, which is the same as the second derivative of the Gompertz Equation (9). This implies that at that point where the growth speed is at maximum, the Gompertz function has a turning point:

$$\frac{d^2X}{dt^2} = a \cdot c^2 \cdot e^{[-e^{-ct+b}]} \cdot (e^{-ct+b})^2 - a \cdot c^2 \cdot e^{[-e^{-ct+b}]} \cdot (e^{-ct+b})$$

$$\frac{d^2X}{dt^2} = a \cdot c^2 \cdot e^{[-e^{-ct+b}]} \cdot (e^{-ct+b}) \cdot [(e^{-ct+b}) - 1]$$

$$\frac{d^2X}{dt^2} = a \cdot c^2 \cdot e^{[-e^{-ct_m+b}]} \cdot (e^{-ct_m+b}) \cdot [(e^{-ct_m+b}) - 1] = 0$$

$$-ct_m + b = 0$$

$$t_m = \frac{b}{c}$$

The concentration of cells where the maximum reproduction speed occurs is calculated by entering the value of t_m in Equation (10), and it is shown that the growth rate where the reproduction speed is at maximum equals c :

$$X = a \cdot e^{[-e^{-ct_m+b}]} = a \cdot e^{[-e^{-ct_m+b}]} = \frac{a}{e}$$

$$\mu_m = c \cdot \ln(a/(a/e)) = c$$

The maximum reproduction speed value is obtained by substituting t_m in Equation (10):

$$v_{max} = \frac{dX_{tm}}{dt} = a \cdot c \cdot e^{[-e^{-ct_m+b}]} \cdot e^{-ct_m+b} \cdot a \cdot c \cdot e^{[-e^{-c\frac{b}{c}+b}]} \cdot e^{-c\frac{b}{c}+b} = \frac{a \cdot c}{e}$$

The curve tangent X in the point of inflection t_m has the form:

$$X = \frac{a \cdot c}{e} t + k$$

$$\text{Given the } t = t_m = \frac{b}{c} \text{ } yX_{tm} = \frac{a}{e} \text{ so:}$$

$$\frac{a}{e} = \frac{a \cdot c}{e} \cdot \frac{b}{c} + k = \frac{a}{e} - \frac{a \cdot b}{e} = \frac{a}{e} (1 - b)$$

$$X = \frac{a \cdot c}{e} t + \frac{a}{e} (1 - b) = \frac{a}{e} \cdot (ct + (1 - b))$$

Meanwhile, the latency time, t_{lag} , is the time in which the tangent line at the curve inflection point (point that coincides with maximum velocity) cuts the axis of the abscissa. In this case, the latency time is in $X = 0$:

$$0 = ct_{lag} + (1 - b)$$

$$t_{lag} = \frac{(b - 1)}{c}$$

From this equation, b can also be expressed as:

$$b = c \cdot t_{lag} + 1$$

$$v_{max} = \frac{a \cdot c}{e}$$

$$b = \frac{v_{max}}{a} \cdot t_{lag} + 1$$

Finally Equation (11) becomes the modified Gompertz equation:

$$X = a \cdot e \left[-e^{-\frac{v_{max}}{a}(t_{lag} + 1) + 1} \right] \quad (11)$$

Several researchers have found the modified Gompertz model (equation 11) to be useful and applied it in their work (Bah *et al.*, 2014; Capson-Tojo *et al.*, 2017; Bayrakdar *et al.*, 2018; Mancini *et al.*, 2018; Martín *et al.*, 2018; Li *et al.*, 2018). It is equally possible to experimentally determine the maximum reproduction speed and the latency time, in this case, X is measured as well as the reactor time (Velazquez-Martí *et al.*, 2019). Next by defining the value of the constant (a) as the maximum cell concentration obtainable, Equation (11) then can be linearized to have Equation (12):

$$\ln \left(\ln \frac{X}{a} \right) = -\frac{v_{max} \cdot e}{a} t + \left(1 + \frac{v_{max} \cdot e}{a} t_{lag} \right) \quad (12)$$

The latency time and the maximum speed of cellular reproduction will be the characteristics of the microbial group in certain conditions (Velazquez-Martí *et al.*, 2019).

Obviously, the Gompertz model provides an equation that describes cell concentration over time in a biodigestion process. However, the three constants: a which represents the maximum cellular concentration, b which is a constant that depends on the initial concentration of cells and a, and c which is the value of the cell growth rate where the growth velocity is at maximum, that is, at the inflection point of the curve can be empirically generated. It can be concluded that the Gompertz model does not recognize the existence of maximum cell growth rate. This is attributed to the fact that the maximum rate value considered in the exponential phase by Monod and his colleagues is minorized when the substrate concentration is low.

4.3: Biokinetics (Empirical) Models

The development of biokinetic models provides a better representation of real AD processes (Matheri *et al.*, 2017). Biokinetics model is described by three phenomena: substrate consumption, microbial growth and decay, methane production and inhibition of microbial activity. The emergence of the 'black-box' model is due to the complexity of the Gompertz model and the problems that exist when applying the exponential models despite the complementary role of the Monod model. Consequently, several researchers decided to develop models that do not focus on the growth rate but on the kinetics of the substrate degradation or product formation. In view of this development, Brulé *et al.* (2014) classify the kinetic models into four groups: first-order kinetics with a single step reaction, first-order kinetics with two-step reaction, first-order kinetics with a single step reaction in two speeds and first-order kinetics with a two step reaction in two speeds.

4.3.1: First-Order Kinetics with Single Step Reaction

This model proposed that the rate of digestion is proportional to the amount of substrate. This is described as shown in Equation (13).

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = k \cdot S$$

$$S = S_0 \cdot e^{-k \cdot t} \quad (13)$$

where S is the amount of substrate at a time t , S_0 is the initial substrate amount, and k is the kinetic constant. However, as the mass (M) in the reaction is conserved, the mass of product M (methane) is evaluated using Equation (14).

$$M = S_0 \cdot (1 - e^{-k \cdot t}) \quad (14)$$

Researchers such as: Angelidakiet *al.* (2009) have used this kinetic type of model. The concentration of methane that is generated in a digester with the maximum potential can be described using Equation (15).

$$\ln \frac{M_e - M}{M_e} = -k \cdot t$$

$$M = M_e \cdot (1 - e^{-k \cdot t}) \quad (15)$$

where M is the methane produced at a given time t , M_e is the value of the final methane production, and k is the constant of the hydrolysis rate (Velazquez-Marti *et al.*, 2019).

Furthermore, Díaz *et al.* (2011) evaluated the digestion of cellulose with manure by comparing the first-order equation, including in the equation (16) are the latency time and the modified Gompertz equation terms. They found that both models did not offer significant differences in the coefficient of determination obtained in the models (r^2), neither in the methane potential predicted M_e nor between the constant kinetics k and v_{Mmax} . However, it shows that the first-order kinetic model provides a longer latency time. The maximum methane potential M_e was between 0.30 and 0.33 m^3/kg SV (Velazquez-Marti *et al.*, 2019).

$$M = M_e \cdot (1 - e^{-k \cdot (t - t_{lag})}) \quad (16)$$

Zhang *et al.* (2018) also compared the modified Gompertz equation and the first order kinetic model according to Equation (16). It was found that the first-order kinetic model provides longer latency times and methane potentials than Gompertz. However, it provides slightly lower coefficients of determination.

4.3.2: First-Order Kinetics with Two-Step Reaction

This model has been one of the popular biokinetics models ever proposed (Velazquez-Marti *et al.*, 2019). Shin and Song (1995) investigated anaerobic digestion process and considered it to be a two-step process that could work at different speeds. Although this comprises a complex hydrolytic, acetogenic, and methanogenic process, a more suitable kinetic model than the previous one (first-order kinetics with a single step reaction). The model first considers the formation of volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from the substrate (S) and, subsequently, the conversion of these acids (VFAs) into methane (M).

As the name implies, the formation of volatile fatty acids depends on the substrate concentration, following first-order kinetics, where k_1 is the kinetic constant of transformation of the substrate to VFA, S is the substrate concentration, and S_{VFA} is the concentration of acid grades (Equation 17):

$$\frac{dS_{VFA}}{dt} = k_1 \cdot S \quad (17)$$

Given the $S = S_0 \cdot e^{-k_1 \cdot t}$, Equation (17) becomes Equation (18)

$$\frac{dS_{VFA}}{dt} k_1 \cdot S_0 \cdot e^{-k_1 \cdot t} \quad (18)$$

However, the elimination of the fatty acids is reported to depend on the concentration of the substrate, also following first-order kinetics, being k_2 as the kinetic constant of transformation of the VFA to M.

Accounting for mass balance in the formation of the VFA, a differential equation of constant coefficients of first order Equation (19) is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS_{VFA}}{dt} &= k_1 \cdot S_0 \cdot e^{-k_1 \cdot t} - k_2 \cdot S_{VFA} \\ \frac{dS_{VFA}}{dt} + k_2 \cdot S_{VFA} &= k_1 \cdot S_0 \cdot e^{-k_1 \cdot t} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

such as:

$$\begin{aligned} y + a(x) \cdot y &= b(x) \\ y &= e^{-\int a(x) dx} \cdot \int b(x) \cdot e^{\int a(x) dx} dx + C \cdot e^{-\int a(x) dx} \end{aligned}$$

The solution to Equation (19) results

$$S_{VFA} = k_1 \cdot S_0 \cdot \frac{e^{-k_2 \cdot t} - e^{-k_1 \cdot t}}{k_2 - k_1}$$

From this equation, the accumulated methane production is obtained as (Equation 20)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dM}{dt} &= k_2 \cdot S_{VFA} \\ \frac{dM}{dt} &= k_2 \cdot k_1 \cdot S_0 \cdot \frac{e^{-k_2 \cdot t} - e^{-k_1 \cdot t}}{k_2 - k_1} \\ M &= S_0 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{k_1 e^{-k_2 \cdot t} - k_2 e^{-k_1 \cdot t}}{k_2 - k_1} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

4.3.3: First-Order Kinetics with a Single Step Reaction in Two Speeds

During digestion process, the chemical composition of the substrates is generally heterogeneous and can be constituted by several fractions with different hydrolysis rates. This implies that the process has two parallel but independent mechanisms that occur simultaneously. Defining a as the relation between the amount of rapidly degradable substrate and k_F as the first-order kinetic constant for degradation of rapidly degradable substrate, and k_L as the first-order kinetic constant for the degradation of slowly degradable substrate, the amount of methane (M) produced can be defined with the model (Equation 21) used by Kusch *et al.* (2008) as well as Luna *et al.* (2011):

$$M = S_e \cdot (1 - a \cdot e^{-k_F \cdot t} - (1 - a) \cdot e^{-k_L \cdot t}) \quad (21)$$

Dennehy *et al.* (2016) compared three different kinetic models to determine the most suitable to describe the kinetics of the discontinuous co-digestion of food waste and pig manure at 37°C: (1) first order, (2) Gompertz, and (3) two-speed one-step reaction with first-order kinetics. They found that the three models provide similar determination coefficients; however, the RMSE (root of the mean of the squares of the errors) is significantly reduced when the two-speed digestion is considered. The worst RMSE was for the Gompertz model. The first-order kinetic model reduced the RMSE by 39%, and the first-order kinetic model

with two speeds reduced the RMSE by 80%. The highest methane yields they obtained were $0.521 \pm 29 \text{ m}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ VS}$ (Velazquez-Marti *et al.*, 2019).

4.3.4: First-Order Kinetics with a Two Step Reaction in Two Speeds

This model considered two steps in each of the fractions of which the substrate is composed, both for the rapidly degradable substrate fraction and for the slowly degradable substrate fraction. Equation (22) describes the two steps process vividly.

$$M = S_e \cdot \left[a \left(1 - \frac{k_{HF} e^{-k_{MF} \cdot t} - k_{MF} e^{-k_{MF} \cdot t}}{k_{HF} - k_{MF}} \right) + (1 - a) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{k_{HL} e^{-k_{ML} \cdot t} - k_{ML} e^{-k_{HL} \cdot t}}{k_{HL} - k_{ML}} \right) \right] \quad (22)$$

Brule *et al.* (2014) evaluated the four kinetic models described so far and found that the models that consider an easy speed in both a step and two steps yield a reasonable estimate. In contrast, the model that considers two speeds with a single step produces overestimates. Therefore, it is considered inadequate. This overestimation is corrected by applying the two-step model at two speeds but complicates its application. Several studies, such as Ghufran and Charles (2004), Li *et al.* (2015), and Zahan *et al.* (2017), have used a function derived from the first-order kinetic model but which substitutes the kinetic constant for the ratio between the maximum and the methane velocity (Equation 23):

$$M = M_e \cdot (1 - e^{-k \cdot (t - t_{lag})})$$

$$M = M_e \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{v_{max} M}{M_e} (t - t_{lag})} \right) \quad (23)$$

4.4: Model Based on the Transfer Function

Several studies, such as Ghufran and Charles (2004), Li *et al.* (2015), or Zahan *et al.* (2017), have used a function derived from the first-order kinetic model but which substitutes the kinetic constant for the ratio between the maximum and the methane velocity (Equation 24).

$$M = M_e \cdot (1 - e^{-k \cdot (t - t_{lag})})$$

$$M = M_e \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{v_{max} M}{M_e} (t - t_{lag})} \right) \quad (24)$$

4.5: Cone model

This model attempts to describes anaerobic digestion process as presented in Equation (25). Several researchers have exploited the model in their work (Pitt *et al.*, 1999; El-Mashad, 2012; Li *et al.*, 2015; Zahan *et al.*, 2017).

$$M = \frac{M_e}{1 + (k \cdot t)^{-n}} \quad (25)$$

5.0: Evaluation of ADM

Several models seek to describe the anaerobic digestion process and the popular ones among them has been reviewed in this paper. However, not all the models satisfactorily decribed the process. Consequently, the model are usually investigated for validation and could be modified where necessary. This is the primary reason why models are evaluated. In view of these, statistical approach to model evaluation has been exploited by most researchers (Velazquez-Marti *et al.*, 2019). Two statistical tools are usually employ in the evaluation

process. These are: (a) coefficient of determination of the fit (r^2) and (b) root of the mean of the squares of the errors (RMSE). Equation (26) is used to calculate RMSE.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(M_{Model} - M_{ob})^2}{n}} \quad (26)$$

Where: M_{model} is the value of methane predicted by the model at an instant t and M_{ob} is the value of methane observed experimentally.

Specifically, several researchers have successfully evaluated the modified Gompertz model, the first-order kinetic model, the transfer function model, and the cone model for anaerobic digestion process using different types of substrates and combinations in co-digestion. In most cases, the values of r^2 , RMSE, and lag time obtained by analysis of variance indicated that all the models provide high coefficients of determination, and there are few differences between them. The transfer model and the first-order kinetic model generally produce higher RMSE, so the modified Gompertz model and the cone model make more accurate estimates. However, the Gompertz model estimates higher latency periods (Pitt *et al.*, 1999; Ghufuran and Charles, 2004; El-Mashad, 2013; Li *et al.*, 2015; Zahan *et al.*, 2018). Different adaptations to fit the variables to the obtained values in the experiments are currently subjects of research interest. It is expected that the models would be harnessed for optimization of the process and as well proffer solutions to problems challenging the technology.

6.0 Conclusion

Anaerobic digestion process has been exploited primarily for waste management/treatment technology for several centuries. It has an edge over its counterparts as it proffers solution to energy and soil fertility problems. However, it is still a subject of research interest due to the variability of process conditions in which can be operated, diversity of bio-sourced feedstock, and other influential factors. In addition, the technology is generally slow and unstable with relatively poor yield.

There is a growing research interest aimed at improving the process and the literature is flooded on the subject. Model is one of the tools developed to understand the process better. It is exploited not only to predict the system's performance but also for optimization for improved production. The search for appropriate models is currently a major priority for optimizing the process. It is widely accepted that AD is a four-stage process. The models developed so far majorly described the process at each of the stages. However, most of their descriptions are not valid for the entire process. Several models have been developed in an attempt to describe and improve the process.

This paper reviewed the prominent ones among them. The pioneer model (exponential model) which is a mathematical model is not valid beyond the growth phase as the exponential growth ceases. However, Monod's model predicts the presence of the maximum cell growth as the cell reached its zenith. Several models emerged to advance Monod's description. Prominent among them is Contois' model. However, the maximum rate value predicted in the exponential phase is minorized when the substrate concentration is depleted. Consequently, the mathematical models failed to describe cell behavior at stationary phase. Knowledge of cell behavior in this phase is significantly relevant especially

when high retention times and ‘digestate’ valorization are desired. Hence, the emergence of Gompertz (statistical) models which tend to describe cell growth rate during stationary phase yet does not acknowledge the existence of maximum cell growth rate.

Generally, the complexity of the Gompertz models and the problems that exist when applying the derivatives of the Monod and Contois equation have led some researchers to suggest models that do not focus on the growth rate but on the kinetics of substrate degradation or product formation. Four categories of biokinetics (experimental) models emerged describing AD process based on production rate. Consequently, there are: first-order kinetic model, model based on transfer function, and cone model emanating from different types of substrates and combinations in co-digestion. It is found that anaerobic digestion processes are more of waste management/treatment strategy than energy production irrespective of the substrate combo as methane potential (energy source) is relatively less than that of the conventional energy. Different adaptations to fit the variables to the obtained values in the experiments have been reviewed. It is expected that the models would be harnessed for optimization of the process and as well proffer solutions to problems challenging the technology.

7.0 References

- Aboudi, K., Álvarez-Gallego C. J. and Romero-García, L. I. (2016). Evaluation of methane generation and process stability from anaerobic co-digestion of sugar beet by-product and cow manure. *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering*. 121(5):566-572.
- Aboudi, K., Álvarez-Gallego C. J. and Romero-García, L. I. (2015). Semi-continuous anaerobic co-digestion of sugar beet byproduct and pig manure: Effect of the organic loading rate (OLR) on process performance. *Bioresource Technology*, 194:283-290.
- Agyeman, F. O. and Tao, W. (2014) Anaerobic co-digestion of food waste and dairy manure: Effects of food waste particle size and organic loading rate. *Journal of Environmental Management*;133: 268-274.
- Ampomah-Benefo, K., Bofo-Mensah, G., Animpong, M. A., Oduro, W. O., Kotey, E. N., Akufo-Kumi, K. and Laryea, G. N. (2013). Thermal Efficiency of Charcoal Fired Cook stoves in Ghana. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Engineering, Technology and Innovation*, 2(3):102-110.
- Ampomah-Benefo, Kofi (2018) A Prototype of an Adaptive, Multi-Feedstock, Anaerobic Biomass Digester for Biogas Production, PhD Thesis, University of Ghana, Legon.
- Angelidaki, I., Alves M., Bolzonella, D., Borzacconi, L., Campos, J. L. And Guwy A. J. (2009). Defining the biomethane potential (BMP) of solid organic wastes and energy crops. A proposed protocol for batch assays. *Water Science and Technology*. 59(5):927-934.
- Arvanitoyannis, I. S., Kassaveti, A and Stefanatos, S. (2007) *Int. J. Food Sci. Tech.*42 (7): 852 – 867.
- Bah, H., Zhang, W., Wu, S., Qi, D., Kizito, S. and Dong, R. (2014). Evaluation of batch anaerobic co-digestion of palm pressed fiber and cattle manure under mesophilic conditions. *Waste Management*. 34(11):1984-1991.

- Bamgboye, I. A. (2012). The potential of producing fuel from biomass in Nigeria In: Jekayinfa S. O. (Ed). Building a non-oil export based economy for Nigeria: the potential of value -added products from agricultural residues. *CuvillierVerlag Gottingen*. pp. 35-41.
- Batstone, D.J., Boe, K. and Angelidaki, I. (2007). An innovative online VFA monitoring system for the anerobic process, based on headspace gas chromatography. *Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, 96 (4): 712-721.
- Bayrakdar, A., Sürmeli, R. Ö.andÇalli, B. (2018). Anaerobic digestion of chicken manure by a leach-bed process coupled with side-stream membrane ammonia separation. *Bioresource Technology*, 258:41-47.
- Belle, A. .J, Lansing, S., Mulbry, W. and Weil, R. R. (2015). Anaerobic co-digestion of forage radish and dairy manure in complete mix digesters. *Bioresource Technology*.178:230-237.
- Bhat P.R., Chanakya H.N. and Ravindranath N.H. (2001) *J. Energy Sust. Dev.*, 1:39 – 41.
- Brulé, M.Oechsner, H. andJungbluth, T. (2014). Exponential model describing methane production kinetics in batch anaerobic digestion: A tool for evaluation ofbiochemical methane potential assays.*Bioprocess and Biosystems Engineering*.37(9):1759-1770.
- Buysman, E. and Mol, A. P. J. (2013). Market-based biogas sector development in least developed countries—the case of Cambodia. *Energy Policy*, 63:44–51.
- Capson-Tojo G, Rouez M, Crest M, Trably E, Steyer J-P, Bernet N. (2017). Kinetic study of dry anaerobic codigestion of food waste and cardboard for methane production. *Waste Management*.69:470-479.
- Cestonaro, T., Costa MSS de M, C., Rozatti, M. T., Pereira, D. C., Francisconi, H. E. (2015) The anaerobic co-digestion of sheep bedding and $\geq 50\%$ cattle manure increases biogas production and improves biofertilizer quality. *Waste Management*, 46:612-618.
- Cheng, L-L, Lee, Y-H, Lin, J-H, Chou, M-S. (2010). Treatment of mixture of sewage and partially treated swine wastewater by a combination of UASB and constructed wetlands. *Practice Periodical of Hazardous, Toxic, and Radioactive Waste Management*, 14 (4): 234-239.
- Chynoweth, D. P., Wilkie, A. C. and Owens, J. M. (1998). Anaerobic processing of piggery wastes: A review. In: ASAE Annual International Meeting; 12–16 July. Orlando, Florida, USA: St Joseph: American Society of Agricultural Engineers (ASAE). P.38.
- Conrad, R. (1999). Contribution of Hdrogen to Methane Production and Control of Hydrogen Concentrations in Methanogenic Soils and Sediments. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, 28: 193-202.

- Dennehy, C., Lawlor, P. G., Croize, T., Jiang, Y., Morrison, L., Gardiner, G. E. (2016). Synergism and effect of high initial volatile fatty acid concentrations during food waste and pig manure anaerobic co-digestion. *Waste Management*. 56:173-180.
- Di Maria, F., Sordi, A., Cirulli, G. and Micale C. (2015). Amount of energy recoverable from an existing sludge digester with the co-digestion with fruit and vegetable waste at reduced retention time. *Applied Energy*. 150:9-14.
- Díaz, I., Donoso-Bravo, A. and Fdz-Polanco, M. (2011). Effect of microaerobic conditions on the degradation kinetics of cellulose. *Bioresource Technology*.102(21):10139-10142.
- Edenseting, B. O., Obonukut, M. E. and Oboh, I. O. (2020) Bio-Sourced Feedstocks for Biofuel Production: Nigeria as a Case Study. *bJournal of Scientific and Engineering Research*. 7(12): 1-18.
- El-Mashad, H. M. (2013). Kinetics of methane production from the codigestion of switchgrass and *Spirulina platensis*algae. *Bioresource Technology*. 132:305-312.
- Fedailaine, M.Moussi, K.,Khitous, M., Abada, S., Saber, M. andTirichine, N. (2015). Modelling of Anaerobic Digestion of Organic Waste for Biogas Production. *Procedia Computer Science* 52:730-737.
- Fekadu, M (2014). *Biogas production from Water Hyacinth (eichhorniacrassipes) Co-digestion with cow-dung*.M.Sc thesis, Haramaya University.
- Ferry, J. G. (2011).Fundamentals of Methanogenic Pathways that are Key to the Biomethanation of Complex Biomass, *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, 22, 351-357.
- Franco, R. T., Buffière, P. and Bayard, R. (2018).. Coensiling of cattle manure before biogas production: Effects of fermentation stimulants and inhibitors on biomass and methane preservation. *Renewable Energy*,121:315-323.
- Fu, S. F., Wang, F., Yuan, X. Z., Yang, Z. M., Luo, S. J. and Wang, C. S. (2015). The thermophilic (55°C) microaerobic pretreatment of corn straw for anaerobic digestion. *Bioresource Technology*,175:203-208.
- Fu, S. F., Shi, X. S., Xu, X. H., Wang, C. S., Wang, L. and Dai, M. (2015) Secondary thermophilicmicroaerobic treatment in the anaerobic digestion of corn straw. *Bioresource Technology*,186:321-324.
- Ghufran, R. and Charles, B. (2004)The use of a specific function to estimate maximum methane production in a batch-fed anaerobic reactor. *Journal of Chemical Technology and Biotechnology*. 79(10):1174-1178.
- Glanpracha, N. and Annachatre, A. P. (2016). Anaerobic co-digestion of cyanide containing cassava pulp with pigmanure. *Bioresource Technology*. 214:112-121.

- Gompertz, B. (2011). On the nature of the function expressive of the law of human mortality, and on a new mode on determining the value of live contingencies. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*. 115:513-585
- Guo, J., Cui, X., Sun, H., Zhao, Q., Wen, X. and Pang, C. (2018). Effect of glucose and cellulase addition on wet-storage of excessively wilted maize stover and biogas production. *Bioresource Technology*, 259:198-206.
- Gwavuya, S. G., Abele, S., Barfuss, Z. M. and Müller, J. (2012). Household energy economics in rural Ethiopia: a cost-benefit analysis of biogas energy. *Renew Energy*;48:202–9.
- Herrmann, C., Idler, C. and Heiermann, M. (2016). Biogas Crops Grown in Energy Crop Rotations: Linking Chemical Composition and Methane Production Characteristics. *Bioresource Technology*, 206:23-35.
- Johari, A., Ahmed S.I., Hashim H., Alkali H., Ramli M. (2012). Economic and Environmental Benefits of Landfill Gas from Municipal Solid Waste in Malaysia, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 16 (5), 2907-2919.
- Kabir, H., Yegbemey, R. N. and Bauer, S. (2013). Factors determinant of biogas adoption in Bangladesh. *Renew. Sustain Energy Rev*; 28:881–9.
- Kozo, I., Hisajima, S. and Dangh, R. J. (1996) Utilization of Agricultural wastes for biogas production in Indonesia, In: *Traditional technology for environmental conservation and sustainable development in the Asia Pacific region*. 9:134 – 138.
- Krich, K. (2005) *Biomethane from Dairy Waste A Sourcebook for the Production and Use of Renewable Natural Gas in California* Singapore: Prentice Hall.
- Kusch, S., Oechsner H, Jungbluth T. (2008). Biogas production with horse dung in solid-phase digestion systems. *Bioresource Technology*. 99:1280-1292.
- Landi, M., Sovacool, B. K. and Eidsness, J. (2013). Cooking with gas: policy lessons from Rwanda's National Domestic Biogas Program (NDBP). *Energy Sustain. Dev*; 17:347–56.
- Laramee, J., Davis, J. Eserit, Y. (2013). Economic and environmental impacts of domestic bio- digesters: Evidence from Arusha, Tanzania. *Energy Sustain Dev*. 17: 296–304.
- Li, K, Liu R. and Sun C.(2015). Comparison of anaerobic digestion characteristics and kinetics of four livestock manures with different substrate concentrations. *Bioresource Technology*. 198:133-140.
- Li, W., Siddhu MAH, A. F., He, Y, Zhang, R. and Liu, G. (2018). Methane production through anaerobic codigestion of sheep dung and wastepaper. *Energy Conversion and Management*.156:279-287.
- Li, Y., Liu, H., Yan, F., Su, D., Wang, Y., and Zhou, H. (2017). High-Calorific Biogas Production from Anaerobic Digestion of Food Waste Using a Two-phase Pressurized Biofilm (TPPB) System. *Bio-resource Technology*, 224:56-62.

- Luna, del Risco M, Normak A, Orupold K. (2011) Biochemical methane potential of different organic wastes and energy crops from Estonia. *Agronomy Research*. 9:331-342
- Mancini, G., Papirio, S., Lens P. and Esposito G. (2018). Increased biogas production from wheat straw by chemical pretreatments. *Renewable Energy*. 119:608-614.
- Mara, D. and Horan, N. (2003). *The Handbook of Water and Wastewater Microbiology*. London: Academic Press.
- Marin Batista J, Salazar L, Castro L, Escalante-Hernández H. (2016). Co-digestión anaerobia de vinaza y gallinaza de jaula: alternativa para el manejo de residuos agrícolas colombianos. *Revista Colombiana de Biotecnología* 18(2):6-12.
- Matheri, A.N., S.N. Ndiweni, M. Belaid, E. Muzenda, and R. Hubert (2017). Optimising biogas production from anaerobic co-digestion of chicken manure and organic fraction of municipal solid waste. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 80: 756-764.
- Martín, Juárez J, Riol Pastor E, Fernández Sevilla J. M, Muñoz Torre R, García-Encina PA, Bolado Rodríguez S (2018). Effect of pretreatments on biogas production from microalgae biomass grown in pig manure treatment plants. *Bioresource Technology*. 257:30-38.
- Mustafa, A. M., Li, H., Radwan, A. A., Sheng, K. and Chen, X.. (2018). Effect of hydrothermal and Ca(OH)₂ pretreatments on anaerobic digestion of sugarcane bagasse for biogas production. *Bioresource Technology*. 259:54-60.
- Nzila, C., Dewulf, J., Spanjers, H., Tuigong, D., Kiriamiti H, L. H. (2012) Multi criteria sustainability assessment of biogas production in Kenya. *Appl Energy*, 93:496–506.
- Obonukut, M. E, Basse, E.N. and Etuk, B.R. (2015) Kinetic Models Evaluation in Methanol Production for Improved Process Design. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*. 4(12):185 – 194.
- Ofoefule, A. U. and Onukwuli, O. D. (2010) Biogas production from blends of bambara nut (*Vigna subterranea*) chaff with some animal and plant wastes. *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 1 (3): 98-105.
- Ofoefule, A. U. and Uzodinma, E. O. (2006) In Proceedings of the IX World Renewable Energy Congress University of Florence, Italy, 19-25UK: Elsevier Publishers.
- Ofoefule, A. U. and Uzodinma, E. O. (2009) *Int. J. Phy Sci*. 4 (7): 398-402.
- Ofoefule, A. U., Uzodinma, E. O. and Onukwuli, O. D. (2009) *Int. J. Phy. Sci*, 4(8):535-539.
- Ojo, O. M; Babatola, J. O. and Akinola, A. O. (2018). Regression Analysis of Biogas Production from the Co-Digestion of Water Hyacinth and Pig Dung. *FUOYE Journal of Engineering and Technology*. 3(2): 141 – 144
- Oparaku, N. F., Ofomatah, A. C. and Okoroigwe, E. C. (2013) Biodigestion of cassava peels blended with pig dung for methane generation *Academic Journal*, 12(40):5956-5961.

- Pitt R. E, Cross T. L, Pell A. N, Schofield P, Doane P. H. (1999). Use of in vitro gas production models in ruminal kinetics. *Mathematical Biosciences*,159(2):145-163.
- Rajendran, K., Aslanzadeh, S., Johansson, F. and Taherzadeh, M. J. (2013). Experimental and economical evaluation of a novel biogas digester. *Energy Convers. Manage.*;74:183–91.
- Saha, B. C. and Cotta, M. C. (2007). Enzymatic Hydrolysis and Fermentation of Lime Pretreated Wheat Straw to Ethanol. *Journal of Chemical Technology and Biotechnology*, 82:913-919.
- Schack, C. J., McNeil, M. A. and Rinker, R. G. (1989) Methanol Synthesis from Hydrogen, CO₂ and CO over a CuO/ZnO/Al₂O₃ Catalyst I: Steady-State Kinetic Experiments. *Applied Catalysis* 50(1):247-263.
- Shin, H. S. and Song, Y. C. (1995). A model forevaluation of anaerobic degradationcharacteristics of organic waste:Focusing on kinetics, rate-limitingstep. *Environmental Technology*.16:775-784.
- Simeonov I. and Stoyanov S. (2003). Modelling and dynamic compensator control of the anaerobic digestion of organic wastes. *Chem. Biochem. Eng.Q*, 17 (4) : 285–292.
- Suh, Y. J. and Roussaux, P. (2002). An LCA of alternative wastewater sludge treatment scenarios”, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 35:191-200.
- Tchobanoglous G; Burton F. L; Stensel, D. H. (2003).*Wastewater Engineering, Treatment and Reuse*. Fourth edition. Metcalf & Eddy, Inc., McGraw- Hill Science Engineering pp. 629-632, 983-1026.
- Teng, Z., Hua, J., Wang, C. Lu, X. (2014). *Design and optimization principles of biogas reactors in large scale applications*. 4th editionSingapore: MCGraw Hill.
- Tigabu, A. D., Berkhout, F., and Beukering, P. (2013) Technology innovation systems and technology diffusion: Adoption of bio-digestion in an emerging innovation system in Rwanda. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*. 2:285–292.
- Uzodinma, E. O., Ofoefule, A. U., Eze, J. I. and Onwuka, N. D. (2007) *Trends Appl. Sci. Res.* 2(6): 554-558.
- Vavilin, V. A., Fernandez, B., Palatsi, J. and Flotats, X. (2008). Hydrolysis Kinetics in Anaerobic Degradation of Particulate Organic Material: An Overview. *Waste Management*, 28:939–951.
- Vazifekhoran, A. H., Shin, S. G. and Triolo, J. M. (2018). Use of tannery wastewater as an alternative substrate and a pretreatment medium for biogas production. *Bioresource Technology*, 258:64-69.
- Velázquez-Martí, B., Meneses-Quelal, O. W., Gaibor-Chavez, J. and Niño-Ruiz, Z. (2019). Review of Mathematical Models for the Anaerobic Digestion Process In:Intechopen.DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/80815>.

- Wagner, A. O., Malin, C., Gstraunthaler, G. and Illmer, P. (2009). Survival of Selected Pathogens in Diluted Sludge of a Thermophilic Waste Treatment Plant and in NaCl-solution under Aerobic and Anaerobic Conditions. *Waste Management*, 29: 425–429.
- Weiland P. (2010) Biogas production: current state and perspectives. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 85 (4): 849–60.
- Winsor, C. P. (1932). The Gompertz curve as a growth curve. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences. 18:1-8.
- Xu, W., Fu, S., Yang, Z., Lu, J. and Guo, R. (2018) Improved methane production from corn straw by microaerobic pretreatment with a pure bacteria system. *Bioresource Technology*. 259:18-23.
- Zahan, Z., Othman, M. Z. and Muster, T. H. (2018). Anaerobic digestion/co-digestion kinetic potentials of different agroindustrial wastes: A comparative batch study for C/N optimisation. *Waste Management*. 71:663-674.
- Zhang, J. (2017) Three-Stage Anaerobic Digester for Food Waste. *Applied Energy*, 194: 287–295.
- Zwietering MH, Jongenburger I, Rombouts FM, van't Riet K. (1990). Modeling of the bacterial growth curve. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*. 56(6):1875-1881
- Zuru, A. A., Saidu, H., Odum, E. A. and Onuorah, O. A. (1998) *Nig. J. Ren. Ener*, 6 (1 and 2): 43 – 47.